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Функционал овқатланish mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishda o‘simlik xomashyolaridan foydalanish istiqbollari

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Аннотация. Mazkur maqolada an'anaviy va funksional ovqatlarning tarkibiy qismlari sifatida biomodifikatsiyalangan oqsil va polisaxarid mahsulotlari konsentratlarini olish texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish masalalari atroflicha o‘rganildi. Oziq-ovqat oqsillarini ishlab chiqarish uchun ishlatilgan, o‘zining proteolitik fermentlari majmuasi bilan biomodifikatsiyalangan moyli o‘simliklarning urug‘lari – kungaboqar, va zig‘ir urug‘larning biomodifikatsiyasi natijasida asl urug‘larga nisbatan funksional xususiyatli oqsilli mahsulotlar olish texnologiyasi asoslab berildi.

Калит so‘zlar: oqsil, uglevod, inulin, ferment, mikroelementlar, funksional ovqatlanish, biologik faol qo‘shimchalar

Перспективы использования растительного сырья в производстве функциональных продуктов питания

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Аннотация. В статье подробно рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования технологий получения концентратов биомодифицированных белково-полисахаридных продуктов как компонентов традиционных и функциональных продуктов питания. Обоснована технология получения белковых продуктов с функциональными свойствами по сравнению с исходными семенами в результате биомодификации семян масличных культур - подсолнечника и льна - биомодифицированных собственным комплексом протеолитических ферментов, используемых для получения пищевых белков.

Ключевые слова: белок, углевод, инулин, фермент, микроэлементы, функциональное питание, биологически активные добавки.

Prospects for the use of plant raw materials in the production of functional foods

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Abstract. The article examines in detail the issues of improving the technologies for obtaining concentrates of biomodified protein-polysaccharide products as components of traditional and functional foods. The technology for obtaining protein products with functional properties compared to the original seeds as a result of biomodification of oilseeds - sunflower and flax - biomodified with their own complex of proteolytic enzymes used to obtain food proteins is substantiated.

Keywords: protein, carbohydrate, inulin, enzyme, microelements, functional nutrition, biologically active additives.

O‘simlik xomashyosidan olinadigan oqsillar, uglevodlar, mikroelementlar, minerallar va antioksidantlarga asoslangan funktsional, davolash va profilaktik ovqatlanish mahsulotlarini, biologik faol oziq-ovqat qo‘shimchalarini yaratishga qaratilgan texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqish aholining ovqatlanish tarkibini takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi [1].

Ilmiy izlanishlarimiz jarayonida biz an'anaviy va funktsional ovqatlarning tarkibiy qismlari sifatida biomodifikatsiyalangan oqsil va polisaxarid mahsulotlari konsentratlarini olish texnologiyalarini asoslab berdik. Oziq-ovqat oqsillarini ishlab chiqarish uchun ishlatilgan, o‘zining proteolitik fermentlari majmuasi bilan biomodifikatsiyalangan moyli o‘simliklarning urug‘lari - kungaboqar, va zig‘ir /1,2/ urug‘larning biomodifikatsiyasi natijasida asl urug‘larga nisbatan funktsional xususiyatli oqsilli mahsulotlar olindi.

Modifikatsiya natijasida yog‘ni bog‘lash, ko‘piklanish, barqaror emulsiyalar hosil qilish xususiyati yaxshilangan oqsil mahsuloti sifatida surepka, raps, zig‘ir va kungaboqar urug‘lari an'anaviy va funktsional ovqatlanish mahsulotlarining oqsil komponenti sifatida foydalanish istiqbolli ekanligi asoslandi.

Funktsional ovqatlanish mahsulotlari assortimentini kengaytirish uchun an'anaviy va funktsional maqsadli mahsulotlar taklif qilindi, ular jumlasiga topinamburni qo‘shish mumkin, u bir nechta funktsional ingredientlarni o‘z ichiga oladi: inulin, eriydigan va erimaydigan ozuqa tolalari - pektin va kletchatka,

minerallar va vitaminlardir. Erimaydigan ozuqa tolasi (kletchatka) - taxminan 11%, va eruvchan pektin - taxminan 3%, multivitaminlar, makro va mikroelementlar - K, Na, Ca, Mg, P va Fe, Zn, Mn, Se mos ravishda mavjudligi undan FOM ishlab chiqarishda foydalanishga asos bo'ladi.

Topinamburning kimyoviy tarkibi

1-jadval.

Ko'rsatkich	Miqdori, %
Quruq modda	18,0-19,2
Lipidlar	1,2-1,8
Oqsil (N*6,25)	5,0-6,4
Inulin	35,27-47,71
Kletchatka, pektin	10,48-11,17 1,9-3,2

Shunday qilib, topinambur tuganagining kimyoviy tarkibining xususiyatlarini baholash uni an'anaviy va funktsional maqsadlar uchun oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarning biologik faol komponentini olish uchun xom ashyo sifatida ishlatishning oqilona ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Topinambur kukunini olish uchun topinambur yaxshilab yuvildi, tozalandi, maydalab to'g'raldi. Limon kislota bilan ishlangandan keyin 65-70 haroratda qurtildi, son'gra maydalab elakdan o'tkazildi. Olingan kukunning funktsional xususiyatlari aniqlandi.

Topinambur kukunining funktsional hossalari

2-jadval.

Tadqiqot ob'ekti	Funktsional xususiyatlar, %			
Topinambur kukuni	SUX	KX	KB	YUX
	102-160	16-38	54-77	68-91

Suv ushlab qolish xususiyatining nisbatan yuqori bo'lishi o'rganilayotgan namunada gidrofil birikmalar- tola, pektin va oqsil, mavjudligi bilan izohlanadi - ko'pikli qiymatlar ko'piklanish xususiyati va barqarorligi mahsulotni quritish jarayonda yengil denaturatsiyaga uchragan oqsil molekulalarining sirt faol xususiyatlari bilan belgilanadi.

Topinambur kukunini organoleptik baholash shuni ko'rsatdiki, mahsulot och jigarrang kukun, yoqimli shirin ta'mga va engil o'simlik hidiga ega.

Topinambur kukunining funksional xossalari va organoleptik xususiyatlari oziq-ovqat biotexnologiyasi talablariga javob beradi, bu uni polisaxarid sifatida ishlatish imkonini beradi. An'anaviy va funksional mahsulotlarning tarkibidagi biomodifikatsiyalangan oqsil / topinambur kukunining nisbati funksional ovqatlanish statusi korreksiyasi darajasiga qarab o'zgaradi.

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